

Evaluating the Impact of Reformed Research Assessment and the use of Narrative CVs in Academic Career Progression at Swansea University: FAQs and Information Sheet

In 2022, Swansea University began an extensive reform of Academic Career Pathways (ACPs) and Research Assessment in accordance with the Swansea University CoARA (Coalition of the Advancement of Research Assessment) Action plan, linked [here](#). The reformed research assessment process was constructed in collaboration with academic staff, with the goal to better recognise diverse contributions and outcomes made by staff using a more qualitative assessment, moving away from the traditional quantitative indicators previously emphasised in the promotion process. The reformed ACPs were implemented for the first time in September 2024, making you part of the first cohort undertaking the changes to the promotion criteria.

Changes made to the assessment process were as follows:

- Removal of narrow, quantitative KPIs
- Inclusion of two core profile components, alongside contributions to education and research: innovation, engagement & enterprise; and collegiality, leadership & management
- Assessment of research activity utilising a narrative style CV consisting of four domains: Contribution to the generation of knowledge, Contribution to the development of individuals, Contribution to the wider research and innovation community, and Contribution to broader society
- The recognition of Open Research practices (including but not limited to patient/ public involvement, open access, open data, open resources, outreach, exhibitions, co-design of project methods (citizen science), impact and legacies of research, etc.) in promotion applications.

The CoARA Cascade Boost funded project aims to evaluate the impact of these changes on our academic community at Swansea University through an evaluation survey; therefore, your feedback is very important to us. This survey has been designed to gain insight on the experience of the review panels, the experience of the applicants, and whether staff felt they could evidence diverse contributions to research qualitatively. A separate, optional part of the study, asks applicants if they consent to sharing the research capacity element only of their promotion application for linguistic analysis.

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)

We completely understand your questions and concerns and we very much appreciate your interest and engagement in this study. We'd like to answer the questions directed to us from Swansea University's HR to clarify any concerns you may have regarding this project:

- This project has obtained ethical approval from Swansea University's Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences ethics committee (approval number **2 2025 13385 14003**).
- The anonymous survey focuses on feelings and experiences of the academic promotion process, and guidance/ resources available for completing or reviewing applications. There are no questions related to your application asking for identifiable information such as leadership roles, collaborators, publications, or research area.
- All collected data will be held confidentially in accordance with GDPR regulations.
- The second, **optional** part to the study seeks consent to analyse the Research Capacity element of promotion applications. We are interested in representations of concepts such as Open Research, Research Culture, and EDI. We will not review the applications, but aim to identify keywords, recurring themes, and significant concepts in the linguistic data. We will only have access to the Research Capacity element of your promotion application (which will not include other parts of your application) if you give your expressed consent. Any personal or identifying information relating to you, your field, or your work are not relevant to the study and will be redacted in any publications relating to this study.
- If you wish to anonymously participate in the survey but do not consent to having the Research Capacity element of your promotion application (the narrative style CV) analysed that is completely fine! You are welcome to participate in any way that is most comfortable.
- Any shared outputs from this study will have all personal and/or identifying information redacted.